

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF DEVELOPING REFLECTIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract.

In the world, the training of future primary school teachers through the development of reflexive skills of teachers, the development of pedagogical mechanisms for optimizing the educational process is considered one of the main problems of teaching pedagogy. In this article, we are talking about the pedagogical possibilities of developing reflexive skills in students.

Keywords: improvement of reflexive skills, reflexive abilities, pedagogical reflection, reflexive activity.

ENTER

Successful professional formation a primary school teacher, adequate assessment of himself and his professional activity, i.e., to what extent he is the most important factor in his professional school. Mechanisms for organizing reflexive skills development processes in future elementary school teachers are considered as a system consisting of the most effective technologies based on scientific and technical achievements and all scientific tools that teachers prefer in their work. In this case, on the one hand, cooperative activities in the processes of development of reflexive skills, and on the other hand, educational relations become important in improving the processes of development of reflexive skills.

In the processes of developing reflexive skills in future elementary school teachers, the organization of collaborative activities between teachers and students, that is, the formation of subject-subject relations, is carried out on the basis of educational relations, and reflexive skills in this process develops. The development of the processes of educational relations is inextricably linked with the effectiveness of the cooperative activities of teachers and students in a reflexive educational environment and innovative changes.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Scientists of our republic N.N. Azizkhodjaeva, U.Sh. Begimkulov, R.H. Djuraev, Sh.Q. Mardonov, O. Musurmonova, N.A., U.N. Nishonaliev, N.N. Artikov, B. Kh. Rahimov, O'. Q. Tolipov, D. Sharipova, Sh. Shodmonova, N. M. Egamberdieva, A. A. Khalikov and others conducted scientific research.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of development of reflexive skills in the CIS countries L.S. Vygotsky, P. Ya. Galperin, M. G. Davletshin, V. V. Davydov, A. K. Markova, N. V. Kuzmina, S. L. Rubinshtein, E. Goziev and others. It is reflected in the research works.

Issues of creating methodological support for the development of reflexive skills were studied in the works of foreign scientists M. Wallace, Immanuel Kant, Friedrich Hegel, Johann Gottlieb Fichte, Friedrich Wilhelm Schelling and others.

Although certain branches of creative thinking have been shown in the above-mentioned scientific researches, no special research work has been carried out within the framework of the problem of developing reflexive skills in future elementary school teachers.

The effective development of reflexive skills can be achieved through the subjective outlook and perception of the world of the future primary school teacher. Reflexive skills take a deterministic (philosophical doctrine of the connection and interdependence of objective reality and events) position compared to other professional qualities, therefore the educational process in pedagogical universities is organized in this way It is necessary to develop reflexive skills in a special and orderly manner in future elementary school teachers from the first stage (course). Here it is important to distinguish two forms of reflection: reflection in the form of education (in place of “student”) and reflection in the form of organization of education (in place of “pedagogue”).[1]

DISCUSSION

There are the following stages of organizing the process of developing reflexive skills in higher education:

1. To stop activities in science (up to reflection).
2. To restore the sequence of performed actions.
3. To study their (actions) sequence from the point of view of efficiency and productivity of the actions, compliance with the defined tasks. The parameters (size) of the analysis of reflective materials are recommended by the teacher or determined by the students based on their goals.
4. Determining the results of reflection. Such results can be divided into several types:
 - The product of the activity – ideas, suggestions, identified laws, answers to the questions;
 - Methods learned or created (discovered) during the activity;
 - Planning future activities.
5. Checking predictions in the following subjects in practice.

An important factor affecting the effectiveness of the process of developing reflexive skills is the number of forms that respond to the age and other qualities of the participants of the educational process.

If the student cannot independently implement the reflexive process, then in this situation he needs an organizer – a teacher, whose goal is to help the student to realize his reflexive activity, to find his opportunities and shortcomings. Based on this, educational (professional) tasks are determined. There are different forms of educational reflection – group forms (group training sessions) and individual (oral discussion of a situation, filling out a written questionnaire).

Reflective skills are often developed through play activities. Researchers understand the game as an analogue of practical work. The use of games in the development of reflexive skills in educational theory was developed by A.A. Verbitsky. The subject of using educational and educational games is based on the understanding of the quality of human activity, the game is considered to be action models, business games with work models and self-expression models (psychodramas) – role-playing games with communication (sociodramas) produces

To diagnose the reflexive skills developed in students, the teacher can use the following methods: observation, question-and-answer, and analysis of activity products.

RESULT

Observing the reflexive activity of students includes the following: overcoming didactic difficulties that arise in studying educational materials, distinguishing the most basic and important events that happened to them in the process of reflection, aligning the goals and results of the activity, as well as includes the development of assessment and self-assessment criteria. Students can regularly use their reflexive skills, for example, in the form of oral reflection, inquiry or observation. In this case, both external and internal monitoring should be used. External observation is necessary to control behavior, it should be conducted by the teacher. Internal observation or self-observation is conducted by the students themselves and recorded in their performance reports.

Also, in the training, students are recommended to use the method of incomplete sentences to give tasks within the framework of self-observation, in which: “I want to act in such a way that ...”, “Before I start work today...”, “ My following behavior in the next training session...”.

According to T.F. Illarionova, the method of incomplete sentences is used in the organization of the educational process depending on the training sessions and the position of the student in this session.[1] At the end of the topic or section of the studied subject, a written reflexive analysis of the educational activity is conducted.

According to the results of our research, teachers who have reflexive skills today have diversity, subjectivity, creative individuality, professional skills, pedagogical acumen and pedagogical communication culture, benefit from new educational technologies focused on their personal capabilities. Use skills are developed. The goal of modern education is to educate a person who is capable of self-realization, independent education, and self-development.

The content is aimed at self-improvement, creation of conditions for self-expression, self-awareness as a subject of the educational process. This requires prioritization of the problem of training primary school teachers, promoting the development of a person with a high level of professionalism as a leading goal. This ensures the acquisition of not only a system of knowledge, but also a system of skills that provides the ability to effectively perform professional functions. Accordingly, the need to determine and analyze the personal opinion about oneself, one's work and the attitude of the surrounding people requires the development of reflexive skills in future elementary school teachers. Does. As a result of research and on the basis of the theoretical analysis of many national and foreign literatures, we gave our definition of the term "pedagogical reflection" in our dissertation:

Pedagogical reflection is the ability of the intellect to objectify its mental process, to perceive and analyze its activity. It is also considered a mechanism of self-analysis, it becomes a means of controlling one's own activities, understanding, responsible behavior, and allows observing cause-effect relationships in one's personal world. These features constitute the essence and importance of pedagogical reflection.

Relying on the opinion of the author of reflexive pedagogy [1], the competences that are formed during training in pedagogical higher educational institutions can serve as a source of professional growth of the future elementary school teacher only if they are the object of systematic analysis. We can say that it is possible. Unreflective learning activities of students are considered useless and over time lead to professional stagnation (professional stagnation) rather than professional development.

Therefore, in the process of studying the subject of "Pedagogical skills", students of primary education and sports educational institutions of pedagogical higher educational institutions will not only acquire new knowledge, but also develop their reflexive skills, reflexive The level and quality of skill development depends on the professional skills of teachers.

CONCLUSION

It is worth noting that, based on S. Yu. Stepanov's scientific work, we can say that in order to develop the reflexive skills of the future elementary school teacher, even if it is minimal, personal practical professional pedagogical activity experience is necessary. Accordingly, in our opinion, it is promising and effective to search for

means of developing reflexive skills at the stage of professional-pedagogical training of primary school teachers [3]

In the concepts of development of reflexive skills shown in psychological and pedagogical literature, special attention is paid to methods of active teaching and methods of actualizing reflection.

References:

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